

Real-time measurements and performance analysis of closed-loop MIMO service for mobile operators

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Abstract: As fifth generation (5G) networks are starting to become commercial, user expectations in terms of new services become high as well. This signifies that mobile communications service providers need to build robust 5G new services as quickly and cost-efficiently as possible. Many new technologies rely on closed-loop (CL) and multiple input multiple output (MIMO) technologies due to emerging cooperation between nodes in next generation networks. In this paper, we first compare different multiantenna transmission modes namely: transmit diversity, open-loop (OL), and CL MIMO spatial multiplexing strategies to provide mobile network operator (MNO) services in terms of their characteristics, limitations and benefits. Later we investigate how launching a large-scale CL MIMO deployment strategy can affect the various key performance indicators (KPIs) of the existing services provided by **Mobile Network Operators (MNOs)** in real-operational network infrastructure in Turkey. Our practical experimental results indicate that, compared to OL MIMO system, CL MIMO can achieve large performance on a practical setup, where up to 3% improvement in cell average throughput, 9% in user throughput, 6% in spectrum efficiency, and 9% in channel quality indicator (CQI) and modulation coding scheme (MCS) are obtained, while reduction by 25% and 17% on sum delay and initial block error rates (IBLER) are observed.

Key words: Closed-loop, multiple input multiple output measurements, real-time testbed

1. Introduction

The **Fifth Generation (5G)** networks are expected to provide low latency, massive connectivity, and high throughput to diverse set of applications and devices. One of the important features of **5G** networks will be to support various subscriber services [1]. Techniques such as **Multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO)** provide significant increase on the effectiveness of the mobile transmission that reduces the radio interference across the cell. Thus, better user experience for **MNOs** services can be achieved as a result. Millimeter-wave (mmWave) based 5G service can be affected by the surrounding environment, such as building shadowing, reflection, rain attenuation, etc. This delay and noise sensitivity would make providing feedback on **Closed-Loop (CL)** systems more critical in terms of their coverage enhancement abilities. The primary requirement to enable **CL** systems is the capability of end-user devices to support the system. Mobile communication systems allow the usage of channel information to implement **CL** techniques between **user equipment (UE)** and **Base Station (BS)**. The information in this channel can be utilized to increase the system's effectiveness without a requirement

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of complex receiver architecture. Moreover, lossless and reliable data transmission with CL systems is also important for some next generation services that are mission-critical and cannot tolerate a single packet loss.

MIMO systems contain multiple antennas to improve the connectivity of UEs. To run MIMO algorithms effectively, a significant coordination support is required between BSs and UEs. In order to utilize all the capabilities of MIMO technology, two types of mechanisms are defined in long term evolution (LTE)-advanced and 5G. These are Open-Loop (OL) and CL MIMO schemes. OL MIMO has been used in the literature in combination with different schemes such as Downlink (DL) multi-user Sparse Code Multiple Access (SCMA) (MU-SCMA) or coordinated multi-point (CoMP) transmission for Ultra Dense Network (UDN) [2]. In time and frequency response of the spatial channel, there are variations that affect the performance of the channel. CL MIMO method leverage the channel feedback information to track these variations accurately [3]. CL MIMO systems are under the focus of industry for 5G communications. 5G New Radio (NR) data transmission is expected to utilize CL MIMO dynamic pre-coding scheme as one way to improve the spectral efficiency [4]. 5G Stand Alone (SA) [5] beam management technique requires CL MIMO system to determine the *best* beam from the UE point of view. CL MIMO solution operates in a dynamic manner, since the mobility of the UE changes in the coverage area. For this reason, it is essential to investigate the performance gains of CL MIMO solution in pre-5G deployments.

2. Related work and motivation

In the literature, many studies on the enhancements and the performance gains for CL and OL based MIMO systems exist. CL and OL based single user MIMO solutions have been studied in combination with Non-Orthogonal Multiple Access (NOMA) in [6]. Closed loop spatial multiplexing (CLSM) scheme is envisioned to be utilized in various 5G applications including UDNs, massive MIMO, and mmWave (and/or terahertz)-based BSs [7]. In [8], a general expression for the probability density function is proposed to derive the system Bit Error Rate (BER) and ergodic capacity in CL for MIMO systems with performance results where it has been shown that ideal CL MIMO provides a 2 dB theoretical performance link gain corresponding to 20% higher spectrum efficiency over OL MIMO. The article in [9] examined the effect of the transmit antenna correlation on the CL throughput of a 2×2 CL MIMO system. Potential learning schemes to achieve and exceed performance of existing MIMO schemes and their performance evaluations using both OL and CL operations in MIMO systems are presented in [10]. The paper in [11] provides a detailed performance comparison between CL and OL MIMO schemes based on system level simulation results and show 2 dB link gain (corresponding to 20% spectral efficiency) theoretical improvements in ideal conditions and 1 dB (corresponding to 10% capacity gain in fully loaded network scenario) when practical constraints are considered. In [12], the impact of different cellular network deployments, antenna configurations, and transmission schemes on achievable performance are examined through theoretical and simulation studies for multiantenna heterogeneous networks (HetNets). System-level simulations are conducted in [13] with the specified aspects mostly affect the capacity and spectrum efficiency of LTE network which also includes CL MIMO. CL MIMO is shown to provide valuable signal-to-interference-plus-noise ratio (SINR) gains compared to OL MIMO via simulations even under Channel Status Information (CSI) feedback error scenarios in [14]. However both of these approaches ([13, 14]) are based on system level simulations that lack experimentation with real-world operational environments inside a MNO infrastructure.

There are also system-level studies for MIMO in the literature. A system level analysis on user-centric

scheduling for a flexible 5G radio design with using **CL MIMO** is presented in [15]. **OL** and **CL** training systems are proposed in [16] as a framework that is using successive channel prediction/estimation at the user for **Frequency Division Duplexing (FDD)**. Relationship between beam-forming and **MIMO** techniques is investigated in [17]. The authors in [18] design a precoding matrix using wider beamwidths in both **CL** and **OL MIMO** transmission schemes to enhance the throughput values for 5G new radio (NR) systems. An iterative algorithm based on an alternating minimization procedure using interference alignment for **MIMO** is proposed in [19]. A method that dynamically configures the transmission parameters for multiple **MIMO** streams is proposed in [20]. **CL MIMO** system is extended for 5G networks in patent [21] so that each receiver is adapted to transmit at least one type of feedback information selected from a antenna selection group. Another **CL MIMO** system patent in [22] is proposing variations on the feedback information, so the payload may be configured to 6 bits including a **Precoding Matrix Index (PMI)** or 4 bits representing a **PMI** and 2 bits representing a differential **SINR**. A detailed comparison of **CL** and **OL MIMO** in **LTE** is given in [11]; however, the analysis results are based on system level simulations. The patent in [23] is proposing a method for dynamic switching between **CL** and **OL MIMO** for multistream processing. The authors in [24] investigate the experimental performances of vehicular throughput of different **transmission modes (TMs)** (including transmit diversity, **OL**, and **CL** spatial multiplexing transmission) in different carrier frequencies and **MIMO** configurations modes. The authors report that **TM-2** mode is shown to be utilized mostly due to its robustness against mobility and poor channel conditions during field measurements of a residential district in İstanbul, Turkey. The paper in [25] investigates the **BER** performances of **CL** and **OL MIMO** schemes using **Minimum Mean Squared Error (MMSE)** and **Zero Forcing (ZF)** equalizers. They report the involved trade-offs of using different equalizers under different **TMs**, but they used **LTE-advanced** link level MATLAB simulator (MathWorks, Inc., Natick, MA, USA). The authors in [26] have derived capacity expressions in terms of the maximum to minimum singular value ratio for both **OL** and **CL MIMO** schemes.

In this paper, approaches different than the ones mentioned above (which are either focusing on simulation based studies or non-practical settings for experimenting with **CL MIMO** solution), we investigate the **MIMO** systems in the perspective of a service that is provided by **MNOs** in a real deployment scenario. While theoretical structure and possible enhancements of **MIMO CL** and **CL** techniques have been studied extensively in literature, there is little information on the service level implementation of **MIMO** techniques for **MNOs** using large-scale deployments. Therefore, our efforts concentrate on addressing the real-world implementation of **CL MIMO** feature in an operational telecommunication infrastructure and observing its effect on large-scale deployment scenarios. **CL MIMO** implementations have been covered in academic literature but little information is available for the **CL MIMO** systems in practical systems when it is provided as a service to **MNO** users. To show the benefits of **CL MIMO** in real-world operational networks, we compare its performance with **OL MIMO** by observing different **Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)** that are used within **MNOs**. Main contributions of this paper can be summarized as follows:

- We use real-telecommunication operator's infrastructure to fully exploit the benefits of **CL MIMO** in large-scale deployment scenarios.
- We provide insights on the benefits and limitations of open and **CL MIMO** implementation scenarios and evaluate their impact on different observed **KPIs** of **evolved Node-B (eNodeB)** for a total of three months in operational network sites in Turkey.

- Our experimental results indicate that **CL MIMO** yields improvements on many **KPIs** (i.e. 6% increase in spectrum efficiency, 9% in user and 3% in cell throughput, higher modulation usage by 27% increase in 64 **Quadrature amplitude modulation (QAM)** utilization, 9% in both **Channel Quality Indicator (CQI)** and **Modulation Coding Scheme (MCS)**, 25% reduced delay and 17% reduced **Initial Block Error Rate (IBLER)**) compared to **OL MIMO** on different cities of Turkey.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section 3 presents the system model and concepts related to different **MIMO** deployment strategies as well as comparisons of **OL** and **CL MIMO** strategies to provide **MNO** services. The experimental results are presented in Section 4 as well as provides discussions on main takeaways issues that need to be considered. Finally, in Section 5, we provide the conclusions and future work of the paper.

3. System model and concepts

We assume that there are K_l **UEs** with N transmit and receive antennas in each cell $l \in \mathcal{L}$ with where $\mathcal{L} = \{1, 2, \dots, L\}$ is the set of cells and L is the total number of cells in the considered geographic region. The channel between **UE-k** in cell l is denoted by $\mathbf{h}_{l,k}^l$ which is a $N \times 1$ vector. In **OL MIMO** transmission scheme (e.g. in **LTE TM-3** mode), the received **DL** signal $y_{l,k} \in \mathcal{C}$ at **UE-k** in cell l is given by

$$y_{l,k} = (\mathbf{h}_{l,k}^j)^H s_{l,k} + \sum_{m=1}^L \sum_{\substack{i=1 \\ (m,i) \neq (l,k)}}^{K_l} (\mathbf{h}_{m,i}^l)^H s_{m,i} + n_{l,k} \quad (1)$$

,

where **BS** l transmits the signal $\mathbf{x}_l = \sum_{i=1}^{K_l} s_{l,i}$ and receiver noise $n_{l,k} = \mathcal{N}_{\mathcal{C}}(0, \sigma^2)$. The received **SINR** at user $k \in \mathcal{K}_l$ is

$$SINR_{l,k} = \frac{|\mathbf{h}_{l,k}^j|^2 P_{l,k}}{\sum_{m=1}^L \sum_{\substack{i=1 \\ (m,i) \neq (l,k)}}^{K_l} P_{m,i} |\mathbf{h}_{m,i}^j|^2 + \sigma^2} \quad (2)$$

,

where $P_{k,l}$ is the transmitted power from **BS** $l \in \mathcal{L}$ to **UE-k**. In **CL MIMO** transmission scheme (e.g. in **LTE TM-4** mode), the received **DL** signal $y_{l,k} \in \mathcal{C}$ at **UE-k** in cell j is given by

$$y_{l,k} = (\mathbf{h}_{l,k}^j)^H \mathbf{w}_{l,k} s_{l,k} + \sum_{m=1}^L \sum_{\substack{i=1 \\ (m,i) \neq (l,k)}}^{K_l} (\mathbf{h}_{m,i}^l)^H \mathbf{w}_{m,i} s_{m,i} + n_{l,k} \quad (3)$$

,

where **BS** l transmits the signal $\mathbf{x}_l = \sum_{i=1}^{K_l} \mathbf{w}_{l,i} s_{l,i}$ and pre-coding vectors $\mathbf{w}_{l,k} \in \mathcal{C}^{M_l}$ satisfy $\mathcal{E}\{\|\mathbf{w}_{l,k}\|^2\} = 1$. The received **SINR** at user $k \in \mathcal{K}_l$ is

$$SINR_{l,k} = \frac{|(\mathbf{w}_{l,k}^j)^H \mathbf{h}_{l,k}^j|^2 P_{l,k}}{\sum_{m=1}^L \sum_{\substack{i=1 \\ (m,i) \neq (l,k)}}^{K_l} P_{m,i} |(\mathbf{w}_{m,i}^j)^H \mathbf{h}_{m,i}^j|^2 + \sigma^2} \quad (4)$$

where $\mathbf{w}_{m,i}^j$ is the pre-coding vector to cancel the interference at cell l for **UE-k**. The throughput of a cellular network in a given area which is measured in bps/km^2 can be calculated as

$$T = B[Mhz] \times D[cells/km^2] \times SE[bps/Hz/cell] \quad (5)$$

, where B is the bandwidth, D is the average cell density, and SE is the per-cell **Spectral Efficiency (SE)** which represents the amount of information transferred per second over a unit bandwidth [27]. In practical **BS** deployments, when **BS** receives the **SINR** values, it first maps it into **CQI** and later into spectral efficiency using 3GPP specification tables (see Table 7.2.3-1 in [28]). Finally it loops through **MCS** indexes to find the best **Transport Block Size (TBS)**- **MCS** pair that can approximate the obtained spectral efficiency and maps an **MCS** index into a **TBS** (see Table 7.1.7.1-1 in [28]) during one **Transmission Time Interval (TTI)**.

3GPP specification has also worked on defining propagation models for urban channels. For urban areas which of interest in our experiments, 3GPP has defined macro-cell propagation model [29]:

$$L = 40 \times (1 - 4 \times 10^{-3} \times Dhb) \times \log_{10}(R) - 18 \times \log_{10}(Dhb) + 21 \times \log_{10}(f) + 80dB \quad (6)$$

, where R is the base station-UE separation in kilometres, f is the carrier frequency in MHz, Dhb is the base station antenna height in metres, measured from the average rooftop level. The **UE** transmit power $P_{l,k}$ from **UE-k** to **BS** $l \in \mathcal{L}$ is

$$P_{l,k} = P_{max} \times \min \left(1, \max \left(R_{min}, \left(\frac{CL}{CL_{x-idle}} \right)^\gamma \right) \right) \quad (7)$$

, where P_{max} is the **UE** maximum transmit power, R_{min} is the minimum power reduction ratio to prevent **UEs** with good channels to transmit at very low power level, CL is the path coupling loss defined as $\max\{\text{path loss} - G_{Tx} - G_{Rx}, \text{MCL}\}$, where path loss is propagation loss plus shadowfading, G_{Tx} is the transmitter antenna gain in the direction of the receiver, G_{Rx} is the receiver antenna gain in the direction of the transmitter, MCL is minimum coupling loss (selected to be 70 dB in macro cell urban areas), $0 < \gamma < 1$ is the balancing factor for **UEs** with bad channel and **UEs** with good channel, and CL_{x-idle} is the x -percentile CL value. [29].

Figure 1 shows the operation of **MIMO** schemes with different classes of **UEs**. Figure 1a shows **OL MIMO** scheme where **UEs** are reporting **CQI** and **Rank Indicator (RI)** values whereas Figure 1b shows **CL MIMO** scheme, where **UEs** reports **CQI**, **RI** and **PMI** values. **RI** is used to indicate the number of **MIMO** layers, **PMI** is used for beamforming operation at **BS** for each layer and **CQI** is used to obtain the required **MCS** index value. **MIMO** works at its best performance if one of the antennas doesn't make interference on to the other antenna. In **MIMO**, **RI** value is very closely related to the number of antennas. In the case of 2×2 **MIMO**, **RI** value may be 1 or 2. If the two antennas do not create interference on each other, then the **RI** value is set to 2, otherwise **RI** value is set to 1. **RI** values supported by **UEs** vary according to **LTE TM** classes [29] of **UEs**. **TM3** or 4 **UEs** support **RI** 1 and 2. **TM2 UEs** do not support **RI** value 2 and operate at **RI** value 1. If the **RI** is 2, the **UE** is able to communicate with two different data streams that have direct affect on the throughput increase. In **UEs** with a **RI** value of 1, the same data streams flow over different antennas. In this case, the throughput is expected to be less, while the data loss due to radio conditions is also expected to be less. **TM3** and **TM4 MIMO** provide higher peak throughput when using rank 2 that allows two code words on two antennas with spatial multiplexing.

Figure 1. Operation of MIMO schemes with different classes of UEs (a) Open-loop MIMO, UEs reporting CQI and RI (b) Closed-Loop MIMO, UEs reporting CQI, RI and PMI.

Table 1 provides the comparisons of MIMO strategies, namely OL transmit diversity, OL, and CL MIMO spatial multiplexing strategies that are experimented in this paper to provide MNO services. OL MIMO schemes are intended for cases when no partial CSI information is available at BSs. In OL MIMO, UE reports only CQI and RI values as CSI. OL MIMO needs low feedback overhead and is more robust against CSI errors. This in turn results in low system complexity. Moreover, OL MIMO is more suitable for high mobility cases. On the other hand, OL MIMO has its own limitations as well. Some of its limitations are as follows: signal matrix is designed irrespective of the channel, UE rotates between all available PMIs and inaccurate PMI selection can decrease capacity gains. On the other hand, OL MIMO exploits both Cyclic Delay Diversity (CDD) and transmit diversity.

At run time, CL MIMO uses accurate channel feedback as an indispensable requirement. CSI in CL MIMO includes CQI, RI and PMI. Feedback information from the UE supports eNodeB to perform link adaptation and beamforming. RI and CQI indicate recommended number of data streams and data rate per stream, respectively. Different than OL MIMO, the PMI in CL MIMO is also reported by UE to the eNodeB so that it can use more suitable codebook for precoding purposes. This can enhance the performance in DL. The feedback method used in CL MIMO can work in both FDD and Time Division Duplexing (TDD). The UE needs to report CSI which is an indicator how good or bad the channel is at a specific time. Based on these reports, eNodeB determines the transport block sizes to send the data, which in turn can be directly converted into throughput. PMI is used to combine the two signals transmitted by the two antennas of eNodeB. The PMI value is measured and reported by UE. This UE based PMI determination method is more suitable for UEs than the one that is

Table 1. Comparisons of multi antenna transmission modes: OL transmit diversity, OL, and CL MIMO spatial multiplexing strategies to provide MNO services.

MIMO Strategy	Characteristics	Limitations	Advantages/ Benefits
Transmit diversity strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — UE reports only CQI. — Uses space-frequency block code in the frequency domain. — Transmit one codeword on each antennas (rank 1 transmission). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Not efficient at high SINRs — Does not enhance the transmission data rate. — Not multistream transmission (due to rank loss). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Provides better coverage and throughput for cell-edge users — Best suited transmission multiantenna scheme at low SINR. — Robust transmission against channel impairments and mobility.
Open loop strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — UE reports CQI and RI. — Does not require any knowledge about the channel at the transmitter. — Transmission on one or two codewords (rank 1 or 2 transmission). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Signal matrix is designed independent from the channel. — UE rotates between all available PMIs. — Inaccurate PMI selection brings less capacity gains. — Suffers from power imbalances over multiple streams and high channel correlations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Low feedback overhead. — Robust against CSI errors. — Low system complexity. — Best for high mobility cases. — Does not bring extra delay with reporting & processing. — Spatial multiplexing can enhance the transmission data rate at high SINR. — Utilizes CDD as well.
Closed loop strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — UE reports CQI, RI and PMI. — Takes time for UE to send the report and for BS to process it. — The decision after the reception of the report will only be applicable in next transmission. — Transmission on one or two codewords (rank 1 or 2 transmission). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Requires accurate channel feedback (to keep channel orthogonality). — Cross-layer interference in case CSI is not estimated well. — Practical difficulties (e.g. channel aging, estimation impairments brings high overhead to UEs). — High challenges in case coordination is required (e.g. in CoMP scenarios). — Small transmission bursts can drain the UE battery (due to frequent CSI feedbacks). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Selects best PMI. — Provides more coverage and throughput. — Suitable for indoor locations. — Effective in conditions where channel is less time-variant. — Great benefit for noncritical services. — Better performance for slow-moving UEs. — Spatial multiplexing can enhance the transmission data rate at high SINR.

chosen by eNodeB in the **OL MIMO**. So, **UE** with **CL MIMO** could receive more powerful signal from eNodeB (array gain) which will improve **CQI** and in turn improve **DL** cell and user throughput. **PMI** is the recommended index indicating the preferred pre-coding matrix. **PMI** information is reported from the **UE** traffic to indicate the preferred set of weights to be applied during the precoding process. The **UE** does this to maximize the link **SINR** rate by providing feedback. **CL MIMO** is more efficient than **OL MIMO** in low mobility environments where user's radio conditions do not change rapidly. **CL MIMO** is expected to provide better results in indoor scenarios where the mobility of **UEs** is low and can be beneficial for noncritical services. Obtaining reliable **CSI** is critical for the operation of **CL** techniques. Some of **CL MIMO**'s limitations are domination of cross-layer interference when **CSI** is not estimated well, practical difficulties such as channel aging, estimation impairments brings high overhead to **UEs** that may exist. Moreover, in case coordination is required either between cells or cells and **UEs** (e.g in **CoMP** [30] or **Single Frequency Network (SFN)** [31] scenarios) the challenges increase. In the **MNO** environment, each eNodeB can be configured separately as **OL** and **CL**. However in **SFN** case, since eNodeBs constitute a single cell, only **OL** or **CL** can be selected which eliminates different **MIMO** configuration flexibility for each eNodeB.

Both **CL** and **OL MIMO** spatial multiplexing schemes support rank 1 and rank 2 transmissions. In case where rank 1 is used, both schemes become similar to transmit diversity. In rank 2 transmission, codewords are transmitted on multiple antennas by using spatial multiplexing. Under certain conditions (e.g at high **SINR**), spatial multiplexing can enhance the transmission data rate. During practical operation, first initial *random access (RA)* transmit diversity is used towards **UEs**. After the reception of *Radio Resource Control (RRC) connection setup* message by **UEs**, **OL** or **CL MIMO** with spatial multiplexing is used. The transmission scheme and correspondingly the **CSI** content is adjusted using **RRC** signaling.

4. Experimental results

We performed experiments for monitoring and comparing **CL** and **OL MIMO** between 02 August 2018 and 31 October 2018 (i.e. for 3 months). During experiments, observation duration during which **OL MIMO** was activated was between August and September 2018, whereas **CL MIMO** was activated in October 2018. The experiments were run in 6 major cities (İstanbul, İzmir, Antalya, Bursa, Kocaeli, and Adana) of Turkey that are located in different geographic regions and **KPIs** are averaged over all the considered locations.

All 3GPP compliant parameters that are used in experiments for **CL** and **OL MIMO** schemes are summarized in Table 2. For configuring frequency bands, **LTE** specific parameters such as carrier frequency, bandwidth, modulation types, etc. are used. Carrier frequency is 800 Mhz (for 10 Mhz bandwidth) or 1800 Mhz (for 20 Mhz bandwidth) and modulation types are QPSK, 16 **QAM** and 64 **QAM**. The experiment parameters and the scenarios in our experimental study match with the specifications proposed by **The 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP)**. All the experiments were done in urban areas which corresponds to urban macro model in [29]. The system scenario is set for the **FDD** system parameters and **FDD** coexistence scenario as specified in [29]. The selected experiment models and the experiment configurations of carriers for transmitters are configured as defined in [32].

Figure 2 shows the **DL** spectrum efficiency values for both **OL** and **CL MIMO** in bits/Hz/sec over the observation duration. Spectrum efficiency measures the bits per **Physical Resource Block (PRB)** in Hz and is calculated as **DL** cell throughput in bits divided by number of **PRBs** used by **Physical Uplink Shared Channel (PUSCH)** dedicated radio bearer per msec, **Resource Block (RB)** in Hz and number of **DL** antennas. We can

Table 2. Parameters used during experimental setup.

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
Total number of eNodeBs (with CL MIMO)	~ 500	# of cells per eNB	3	PDSCH power (avg)	45.8 (dBm)
PDCCH power (avg)	45.4 (dBm)	eNB Antenna gain	17.32 dBi	Antenna pattern	X polarization
eNodeB Max. power	46 dBm	Min. RSRP (Reference signals received power)	-130 dBm	Antenna configuration	2 x 2
LTE duplex mode	FDD	Inter-cell distance (avg.)	305.63 m	System bandwidth	10 & 20 MHz
eNodeB noise figure	5 dB	Carrier frequencies	800 & 1800 MHz	—	—

observe that **CL MIMO** can provide up to 6% improvements compared to **OL MIMO** where the average value increased from 1.37 to 1.44 bits/Hz/sec. Figure 3 shows percentage usage of different modulation schemes where 64 **QAM** usage percentage has increased 27% and **QAM** and 16 **QAM** percentage usage have decreased 17% and 5% respectively. These results clearly demonstrate that together with **CL MIMO**, percentage of higher order modulation utilization has increased.

Figure 2. Comparison of downlink spectrum efficiency of open-loop and closed-loop MIMO.

Figure 4 shows average user and cell throughput values for both **OL** and **CL MIMO** systems. Cell throughput measures the cell capacity. User **DL** throughput has increased 9% and cell **DL** throughput has increased 3% after activation of **CL MIMO** feature in the considered sites. Figure 5 demonstrates the variations of average **CQI** and **MCS** index values in **DL** direction. Compared to **OL MIMO** scheme, average **CQI** and **MCS** values have increased 9% together with the introduction of **CL MIMO** in the considered sites.

Figure 6 shows the comparisons of the sum of **DL** packet delay and **DL IBLER** values for **OL** and **CL MIMO** schemes covering all **UEs**. Together with **CL MIMO**, it is observed that sum of **DL** packet delay and **DL IBLER** values have decreased by 25% and 17%, respectively. These results indicate the importance of application of **CL MIMO** for deployment of critical-services that require low latency and high reliability.

Figure 3. Modulation usability (%) KPI obtained from the real-time testbed.

Figure 4. User and cell downlink throughput KPI obtained from the real-time testbed.

Finally, Figure 7 shows the overall KPI improvements after CL MIMO is activated in different cities of Turkey. We can observe obtained gains in terms of DL user and cell throughput, spectrum efficiency, CQI values, and modulation usability increase in 64 QAM and 16 QAM in different locations of Turkey. The highest increase has been on the usage of 64 QAM, whereas the lowest percentage gains are on cell DL throughput values. On the other hand, QAM usage by BSs has been reduced dramatically by around 40% in all cities. Figure 7 shows that depending on the CQI increments, the highest user DL throughput was experienced in Antalya. The reason for this situation can be explained by the fact that the experimental feature test was

Figure 5. Average CQI and average downlink MCS KPI obtained from the real-time testbed.

Figure 6. Comparison of sum of delay and IBLER between open-loop and closed-loop MIMO.

carried out in the summer months, (i.e. in good weather conditions corresponding to higher number of UEs benefiting from CL MIMO feature activation) and low UE mobility ratios due to the fact that Antalya being a touristic destination city. City of Izmir is the location which exhibits the lowest increment among all other cities. This is due to the low number of UE ratios with CL MIMO support. There is small increment in the number of UEs using 64 QAM in the city of Kocaeli as well. In parallel, there is no major increase in MCS index and CQI values whereas high user DL throughput values have been observed in the city of Kocaeli. This

is due to the existence of high number of **UEs** per cell (i.e. existence of high density cells), which results in high throughput values even when small increments in **MCS** index and **CQI** values occur. In cities of Bursa and Adana, the use of 64 **QAM** and the average **MCS** index values were positively elevated, but this was not reflected proportionally as expected on the **DL** user throughput values in comparison with other cities. One of the reasons for this phenomenon could be that the **CL MIMO** effect is not fully reflected due to high number of inter-cell handovers and possibly high interference levels (as in densely populated cities there are dense base station deployments).

Figure 7. Overall KPIs and corresponding gains after closed-loop MIMO is activated in different cities of Turkey.

Main observations and takeaways: **CL MIMO** is expected to be utilized in combination with different evolving technologies in **5G** networks. For this reason, it is essential to observe its potential benefits in comparison with **OL MIMO** scheme. Note that **CL MIMO** is a mechanism used to continuously adapt the transmitted signal to suit the channel characteristics, whereas, in **OL MIMO**, the communications channel does not utilize explicit information regarding the propagation channel. Hence, the success of **CL MIMO** scheme depends on the quality of channel estimation as the **UE** measures the channel to send reports back to **BS**. On the other hand, potential communication system impairments such as transmit & receive phase differences don't affect the performance of **OL MIMO** scheme. During the observation period of our practical experimental setup, overall improvements have been observed in major **LTE KPIs** including **CQI**, 64 **QAM** usage in **DL**, **UE** & cell throughput, spectral efficiency, packet delay, and **IBLER** values after switching **MIMO** scheme from **OL** to **CL** spatial multiplexing in the considered major cities of Turkey. **CL MIMO** is generally more efficient than **OL MIMO** in low mobility conditions where user's radio conditions don't change rapidly. This signifies that majority of the **UEs** inside the considered sites are in low mobility conditions. However, in locations where high mobility exists (e.g. in highways), it may be more suitable to proceed with **OL MIMO** scheme. Moreover, in specific

locations where high amount of traffic is available, communication overhead of **CL MIMO** can deteriorate the obtained gains in terms of the considered **KPIs**. Therefore, an adaptive approach where appropriate switching capability between **OL** and **CL MIMO** transmission scheme can be necessary depending on the hour of the day (e.g. on peak or low hour traffic) or the characteristics of the locations (e.g. residential, business, shopping area, airport, etc.). On the other hand, the improvements in throughput values were also not too high (around 3% to 9%). This signifies low rank usage choice of **BSs** in **CL MIMO** scheme. Moreover, uncalibrated antennas can also cause for the differences in codeword-quality. Theoretically, **CL MIMO** has been shown to provide up to 2dB theoretical link gain corresponding to up to 20% theoretical spectrum efficiency gain compared to **OL MIMO** schemes as demonstrated in [8] in ideal conditions. On the other hand, our experimental results have indicated that up to 6% for spectrum efficiency gain has been achieved with **CL MIMO** scheme under real operation scenarios. This can be due to nonideal environments where many environmental factors, such as density of the cell, mobility, spatial and temporal patterns of user traffic, BS and UE antenna configurations, etc. as well as impairments related to differences in received signal's amplitude, timing/frequency offsets, and phase noise in **CL MIMO** at the **BS** site that have degraded the performance gains.

Note that **OL** transmit diversity can yield better performances at low **SINR** regimes, whereas **OL** & **CL** spatial multiplexing **MIMO** schemes can work better in high **SINR** regimes (as also demonstrated with system level simulations in [11]). Therefore, depending on the optimal **SINR** point, using transmit diversity or spatial multiplexing schemes need to be decided based on the **KPI** measurements. This can be beneficial for cities such as İzmir, which is observed to have the lowest **MCS** index and **CQI** values. Note also that potential 5G services that can be provided by mmWave (e.g. at 28 GHz) spectrum can be affected by the surrounding environment, such as building shadowing, reflection, rain attenuation, etc. [33]. However, our frequency ranges of eNodeBs used throughout the experiments were on the order of 800 Mhz and 1800 Mhz. Therefore, the effect of such environmental factors, such as atmospheric conditions are not having a big impact on the performance of **CL MIMO** systems.

5. Conclusions

In this paper, we have run real-world experiments on **OL** and **CL MIMO** strategies. We have observed different **KPIs** that are of interest to **MNOs**. First, we have described the characteristics, limitations, and benefits of both **MIMO** transmission schemes. Then, we have run practical experiments to demonstrate the performance gain of **CL MIMO** in major and the most crowded cities of Turkey. Based on the obtained experimental results, **CL MIMO** is shown to outperform 3% **OL MIMO** for cell average throughput, 9% for user throughput, 6% for spectrum efficiency, 9% in **CQI** and **MCS** as well as 25% and 17% reductions on sum delay and **IBLER**. Therefore, **CL MIMO** is demonstrated to be a strong practical candidate technique for future wireless networks via a practical experimental set-up. A possible future study area can focus on the reducing the computational burden at the **UE** introduced by the **CQI**, **RI**, and **PMI** reporting via alternative channel estimation models such as channel transfer functions that are characterizing end-to-end performance. Additionally, an adaptive switch scheme between different **MIMO** modes, which can leverage the strengths of **OL** transmit diversity, **OL** & **CL** spatial multiplexing **MIMO** depending on radio environment, and observing their impact on large-scale nationwide deployments are of interest.

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